

DECICE

DEVICE-EDGE-CLOUD INTELLIGENT COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

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D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan

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Executive Summary

This report, "Dissemination and Communication Plan" summarizes the channels, methods, means and activities that are planned to maximize the impact of the DECICE project through continuous dissemination and communication operations and adds to D6.3 "Online and Media Presence". The dissemination efforts of the project comprise identifying the target groups and stakeholders in the context of the DECICE project and subsequently the planning, performance and reporting of all dissemination activities. In addition, the DECICE project will include stakeholder analyses to identify all relevant stakeholders, their interests and motivations related to the project. Further, it will include networking and cooperation with other EU funded projects by organizing joint meetings and workshops and attending third party events, conferences, workshops, and stakeholder meetings to disseminate the project's results as well as writing peer reviewed articles for publication on the project's results. Several training workshops and hackathons will be organized that illustrate how to use the DECICE solution. Finally, it will include establishing KPIs to evaluate the effectiveness of the dissemination activities. The plan will outline the specific messages for the different stakeholders (e.g., benefits that the project provides to each stakeholder) and the specific communication channels used to deliver them, such as website, social media, newsletters such as events and publications. This task implies also the organization and implementation of a final networking event, which will bring together members of the consortium, expert and advisory board, representatives of the R&D community, industry organizations and decision makers. The event will be an adequate forum to discuss the conclusions of DECICE and ensure its sustainable exploitation beyond the funding period. To ensure the high impact of the DECICE project, all partners are actively involved in the dissemination and exploitation activities and such responsibilities are shared between the consortium partners.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
BoF	birds of a feather
CSA	Coordination & Support Action
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan
DoA	Description of Action
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PWS	Project website
R&D	Research & Development
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
TBA	To be announced
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview

The cloud computing industry has grown massively over the last decade and with that new areas of application have arisen. Some areas require specialized hardware, which needs to be placed in locations close to the user. User requirements such as ultra-low latency, security and location awareness are becoming more and more common, for example, in Smart Cities, industrial automation and data analytics. Modern cloud applications have also become more complex as they usually run on a distributed computer system, split up into components that must run with high availability.

Unifying such diverse systems into centrally controlled compute clusters and providing sophisticated scheduling decisions across them are two major challenges in this field. Scheduling decisions for a cluster consisting of cloud and edge nodes must consider unique characteristics such as variability in node and network capacity. The common solution for orchestrating large clusters is Kubernetes, however, it is designed for reliable homogeneous clusters. Many applications and extensions are available for Kubernetes. Unfortunately, none of them accounts for optimization of both performance and energy or addresses data and job locality. Within this scope, the DECICE project is funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe framework programme and the call „World Leading Data and Computing Technologies 2022 (HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-02)“.

Within a period of 36 months, DECICE aims to develop an AI-based, open and portable cloud management framework for automatic and adaptive optimization and deployment of applications in a federated infrastructure, including computing from the very large (e.g., HPC systems) to the very small (e.g., IoT sensors connected on the edge). Furthermore, DECICE envisions an AI-model, which can use a digital twin of the resources available, to make real-time scheduling decisions based on telemetry data from the resources. Ultimately, the DECICE framework will be able to dynamically balance different workloads, optimize the throughput and latency of the system resources (compute, storage, and network) regarding performance and energy efficiency and quickly adapt to changing conditions. The framework also gives the necessary tools and interfaces for the administrators and deployment experts to interface with all the infrastructure components and control them to achieve the desired result. The integration of the DECICE framework with orchestration systems will be done through open standard APIs to make it portable, modular and extensible. The DECICE framework will be evaluated through established use cases.

The DECICE project will be realized by a consortium of thirteen partners from six different countries. The consortium comprises experts in the cloud computing industry, technology solutions providers, research and service institution, etc.

The project is coordinated by Georg-August-Universität Göttingen Stiftung Öffentlichen Rechts (Germany) and the partners include, next to Gesellschaft für Wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung MBH Göttingen (Germany), E4 Computer Engineering SPA (Italy), Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan (Sweden), the High-Performance Computing Center of the University of Stuttgart (Germany), HUAWEI Technologies Düsseldorf GmbH (Germany), Forschung Burgenland GmbH (Austria), SYNYO GmbH (Austria), Consorzio TOP-IX – Torino e Piemonte Exchange Point (Italy), Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna (Italy), Marmara University (Turkey), BIGTRI Bilisim Anonim Sirketi (Turkey) and The numerical Algorithms Group Limited (UK).

This deliverable is a dynamic document which will be updated in several iterations in order to reflect and introduce upcoming opportunities or challenges related to the dissemination and communication of the project. It highlights selected means, channels, methods and activities for maximising the impact of the project and its practical outcomes.

DECICE will aim to successfully disseminate the project's outcomes and fulfil the project objectives:

- LEVERAGE a compute continuum ranging from Cloud and HPC to Edge and IoT
- AI-SCHEDULER supporting dynamic load balancing for energy efficient compute orchestration, improved use of Green Energy, and automated deployment.
- API that increases control over network, computing and data resources.
- DYNAMIC DIGITAL TWIN of the system with AI-based prediction capabilities
- REAL-LIFE USE CASES of DECICE framework (usability and benefits).
- SERVICE DEPLOYMENT with a high level of trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.

By following the workflow and the strategy, the DECICE project aims to realize the following outcomes:

- An increased awareness of the DECICE project among relevant audiences;
- A clear demonstration of the way EU funding contributes to cloud computing industry as well as researchers, end users and other target audiences;
- Defining and networking with stakeholders who will be interested in using the DECICE solutions;
- Collaborations with other relevant EU projects;
- Constructive engagement, participation and contribution to project events, workshops and other online and offline activities both by the consortium partners and the external stakeholders.

In that way, short- and long-term success of the DECICE project will be enhanced by increasing project visibility, public awareness, and effective communication of achievements to the desired target groups and the scientific community.

1.1.1 Task Description and Methodological Approach

Task Objective

Task 6.1 focuses on the creation of a dissemination and communication plan including the production of online and printed materials such as leaflets, rollups, and posters, etc. in order to ensure the maximisation of the project's impact by spreading awareness and ensuring lasting outreach of the developed outcomes.

Used Methods

For the creation of the dissemination and communication plan, all foreseen dissemination and communication measures, materials and activities were identified and summarized. Each consortium partner investigated individual dissemination & communication for the project objectives, information and results. Furthermore, they described how they plan to contribute to achieving the KPIs mentioned in the Description of Action (DoA).

Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

This deliverable is related to the following other DECICE tasks and deliverables.

Receives inputs from:

Table 1: D6.1 Input from Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable	Due Date	Input for D6.2
T6.1	M1-M36	Dissemination and Communication
T6.3	M18-M36	Establish an Online and Media Presence
D6.3	31.05.2023 (M6)	Online and Media Presence

Provides outputs to:

Table 2: D6.1 Output for Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable	Due Date	Output from D6.2
T6.1	M1-M36	Dissemination and Communication
D6.1	31.10.2024 (M24)	Dissemination and Communication Plan Update
T6.3	M18-M36	Establish an Online and Media Presence
D6.3	31.05.2023 (M6)	Online and Media Presence
D6.3	31.10.2024 (M24)	Online and Media Presence Update

1.1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable starts with **section 1**, the introduction and overview of the project and the document. **Section 2** provides an overview of the project's target audience as well as descriptions of each of the groups. Followed by **section 3**, which outlines the Dissemination and Communication plan, including aims and objectives as well as the process, and **section 4** includes the consortium partner's individual dissemination plans. **Section 5** describes the different dissemination materials utilized for the achievement of the dissemination goals. Followed by the channels and online presence in section 6. In **section 7**, past and future dissemination actions of the consortium partners are being presented. **Section 8** gives an overview of the project's communication activities. **Section 9** outlines the individual dissemination and communication responsibilities of the partners, the management and the monitoring and evaluation of the dissemination activities. The dissemination and communication KPIs are presented in section 10. **Section 11** concludes the deliverable with a summary of the most important points.

2. Relevant Target Groups

To ensure the successful uptake of the DECICE project, relevant target groups have been identified. Those target audiences are reached via the available dissemination and communication channels. DECICE uses different channels and messages to address those parties. See overview in table 3.

Industry and innovators in the IoT, Cloud, Edge (developers/providers of innovative solutions from corporate R&D Labs, IoT innovators leading SMEs and Start-ups, but also “consumers” of the DECICE services and outcomes, candidates for the DECICE services and infrastructure providers).

Research institutes and individual Researchers (academic and corporate researchers and scientists in the fields of IoT, Edge and Cloud computing, communication networks, AI, Big Data, Data Analytics, computer science, etc).

Research initiatives RIAs and CSAs funded under Horizon Europe and other relevant H2020 and 3rd party projects in the IoT, Cloud, Edge, NGI domains, and more.

Standardization bodies, pre-standardization, and open-source initiatives (Standardization bodies and entities focused on the development of interoperable IoT solutions and services, such as ETSI, IEEE, CNCF, the OPC Foundation, the Industrial Internet Consortium, IETF, W3C, and 3GPP; pre-normative bodies such as IRTF, specific study groups and task-forces of ETSI, 5GPP, IEEE; open-source initiatives such as FOSDEM, IOTA, OpenStack, FIWARE, Linux Foundation, Apache, Eclipse Foundation).

European and International Initiatives (Market/Industrial driven initiatives such as AIOTI, ARTEMIS-IA, GAIA- X, SNS/5G PPP, DAIRO/BDVA, FIWARE, Digital Innovation Hubs, etc.).

Policymakers (public national and EU organizations developing relevant regulatory frameworks such as ENISA, BEREC, OECD, governmental initiatives, public authorities, etc.).

Civil society and community at large (social civic organizations, NGOs, the public, media).

3. Dissemination & Communication Plan

Below it will be described how the DECICE project aims to disseminate the results produced in the course of the project. This plan will be updated in M24. The main goal of the dissemination activities is to maximise awareness of the DECICE project's results among the targeted key audiences and eventual stakeholders such as "Industry and innovators in the IoT, Cloud, Edge", "Research institutes and individual Researchers", "Research initiatives RIAs and CSAs", "Standardization bodies, pre-standardization, and open-source initiatives", "European and International Initiatives", "Policymakers" and "Civil society", sister or other relevant projects.

Moreover, the plan includes a detailed methodology to package and present the produced knowledge according to the targeted audiences' needs. Additionally, it serves as an internal communication tool within the consortium.

In this sense, the project will:

- Identify the target audiences and potential stakeholders in order to define concrete and measurable actions for each group to increase the project visibility. Depending on the audience, a different message will be conveyed.
- Use the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the dissemination activities. The regular collection and monitoring of KPIs will enable the DECICE project to adjust the plan and the dissemination activities accordingly.
- Encourage cooperation by networking with stakeholders, projects, communities and networks. The DECICE consortium will identify and map relevant projects, organisations and clusters working in the relevant fields to achieve maximum impact, to avoid duplications and ensure all gaps are filled by the project.

3.1 Dissemination & Communication Aims and Objectives

Borders between communication and dissemination are not always clear, but rather fluid. In general, communication addresses a larger audience with giving more general information about the project itself, while dissemination addresses rather specific target groups which might also have a vivid interest in knowing more not only about the project in general but also about its results. With the planned communication and dissemination activities, the following goals are being targeted:

- Raising awareness and promoting the DECICE project: Delivering general information about content and scope of the project as well as its results to everybody who might be interested, using appropriate channels, is the basis of all communication activities.
- Disseminating the solutions of the DECICE project and their importance for the IT domain.
- Reaching out to specific audiences and stakeholders in order to tailor the various outcomes to the end users' needs from the beginning (cf table 3).
- Fostering further collaborations and enlarging the network by conducting and attending events, workshops, social media interactions etc. and trying to find other EU funded projects, organizations or companies to collaborate with the DECICE project.

The following table gives an overview on how and why specified target audiences will be addressed. The Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for these aims can be found in table 8.

Table 3: Communication & Dissemination Matrix

Target Audience	Benefit/Message:	Communication & Dissemination Channels
Industry and innovators in the IoT, Cloud, Edge	Benefit from DECICE related solutions and combined technologies and resources to minimize up-time-to-market for their applications and services, increased market visibility, participation in the benefit from the project's and 3rd party projects' use cases.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ targeted events ▪ newsletter ▪ project website ▪ project conference ▪ social media ▪ targeted communications ▪ webinars ▪ showcase events ▪ videos ▪ publications
Research institutes and individual Researchers	This group will be engaged in the definition and implementation of the research challenges and spread of the relevant results. DECICE will foster active participation in the discussion and knowledge exchange around the processes and tools of the project, involvement in the project activities and surveys, and create synergies and interactions with the industry and the market through the project ecosystem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ scientific events ▪ publications in international conferences, book chapters and magazines ▪ targeted communications ▪ webinars ▪ online and offline presence and materials ▪ project website ▪ project workshops ▪ presentations ▪ newsletters ▪ social media
Research initiatives RIAs and CSAs	DECICE will match with H2020/HE RIA and CSA projects that have been or are implemented in the relevant domains with the main goal to engage them in the research and in the analysis of the project's results, to retrieve valuable and validated best practices and lessons learned, to jointly promote the results achieved, to engage their existing and live communities, to ensure the most possible visibility and promotion of the project OCs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ targeted communications ▪ social media ▪ project website ▪ project conference ▪ participation in events ▪ promotional material ▪ joint workshops/events /publications/press releases
Standardization bodies, pre-standardization, and open-source	Support technology transfer, liaising with the private sector, innovators, researchers, policymakers, share / promote	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ publications ▪ targeted events ▪ newsletter ▪ project website ▪ social media

initiatives	standards and relevant strategies and success stories, active contributions of DECICE.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ showcase ▪ events
European and International Initiatives	Foster knowledge exchange and collect important information about best practices and approaches, increase their awareness of the European and global challenges in the domain, and promote the research challenges, best practices, and research topics for better design for the future.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ domain experts' events ▪ publications in international conferences and magazines ▪ targeted communications ▪ webinars ▪ online and offline presence and materials ▪ project website ▪ project events ▪ social media
Policymakers	Make informed strategic decisions and plan targeted activities, investments, and calls on DECICE for the good of our economies and societies, liaising with the industry, market, and research worlds.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ local/national events and exhibitions ▪ events at the European level ▪ project website ▪ project conference ▪ newsletters
Civil society	Inform for project advancements, best practices, outcomes, liaise with DECICE stakeholders, awareness on social aspects around project suggested activities and solutions, including the results and use cases of the 3rd party projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ project website ▪ social media channels ▪ newsletter ▪ press releases ▪ press and media communications ▪ publications in dedicated press ▪ organization of and participation at domain-focused events ▪ newsletter ▪ social media ▪ project website

3.2 Dissemination Process

The dissemination and communication process of the project has been planned in order to achieve the best possible outcomes in regards to awareness raising, the enlargement of impact and the dissemination of project results.

At the beginning of the project, the main aim of all dissemination and communication activities is awareness-raising about the project and its objectives among all relevant stakeholders. For this purpose, channels such as the project website, social media channels and newsletters of DECICE and the individual consortium members are being utilized to spread information about the project. Through the consistent use of the project identity, including the designed logo and project colours,

DECICE aims to leave a visual image that can easily be remembered and recalled. Besides the virtual presentations about DECICE, physical materials such as leaflets, roll-ups, folders, posters, stickers and business cards will be provided at this stage already to be used for the purpose of awareness spreading as well as for the dissemination of results in further stages of the project.

In the second stage of the dissemination and communication process, DECICE aims to mobilise and engage audiences and stakeholders to ensure that the solutions are being developed with all their needs and requirements in mind. For this purpose, audiences and stakeholders will be encouraged via social media and other online channels, as well as in the context of in person events and conferences, to share their insights with the consortium.

In the last stage, DECICE will focus on the dissemination of project results in order to spread awareness about these solutions and ensure their impact among stakeholders such as the IT domain, representatives from industry, researchers, and others. To maximise the use and impact of the developed outcomes, the consortium will spread awareness at relevant events and workshops and use previously established communication and dissemination channels as well as newly gained contacts.

4. Individual Dissemination Plans

This chapter outlines the dissemination actions planned by each consortium member. These actions represent initial dissemination plans of the consortium. During the implementation of the dissemination activities and goals, the individual dissemination plans of the consortium partners will be considered. The individual dissemination plans will be reviewed, evaluated and adapted throughout the project, to be aligned with the different stages of the dissemination process to achieve maximum outreach and impact of the planned activities.

These plans are based on the DoA and broken down into single actions, thus allowing for better assessment of their outcomes.

Guiding questions:

- **Publications:** Are you planning to publish any press releases or peer-reviewed publications in relation to the DECICE project?
 - DoA-DEC KPI: 5 publications (in total)
- **Dissemination at events:** Are you planning to disseminate the project objectives or results at any events? If yes, please share some preliminary information regarding the event, event title, event type (conference, etc.), topic of the event, target group, type of engagement (DECICE presentation, etc.)
 - DoA-DEC KPI: 10 presentations on external events (in total)
 - Event Spreadsheet
- **Networking with other projects:** Are you planning to get in contact with other projects funded by the European Commission or any other local, national or international organisation in the context of DECICE? Please provide the project name(s).
- **Events:** Are you planning to contribute to events organised by DECICE? What kind of events? (Options see below)
 - DoA-DEC KPI: 15 workshops/sessions/webinars including:
 - 1 business models workshop (T6.1, M18-M24)
 - 2 requirements workshops (T6.1, 1. in M3-M6, 2. in M7-M12)
 - 6 co-organised webinars/workshops with other H2020 and/or HE funded projects (M1-M36)
 - 1 final event for the presentation of the project results in collaboration with the other RIAs
 - 3 training workshops (T6.1, M12-M36)
- **Videos:** Are you planning to participate/contribute in video creation? (Introduction, informative and educational videos to support awareness creation and stakeholders' engagement). If yes, please share initial ideas in case it is already available.
 - DoA-DEC KPI: 4 videos (in total)
- **Dissemination channels:** Which internal dissemination channels are you using or are you planning to use to disseminate information regarding DECICE (e.g., websites, blogs,

newsletters, social media channels of your organisation, etc.)? How are you using these channels to disseminate information regarding DECICE?

- **Stakeholder engagement and networks:** Which stakeholders are you planning to engage with regarding the dissemination activities of DECICE and how are you planning this engagement (e.g., industry and innovators, researcher and research institutes, other projects (sister projects, RIAs, CSAs, etc.), standardisation bodies, European and international initiatives, policymakers, civil society, press, media, etc.)? Are there any stakeholder networks that you are planning to utilise for dissemination activities?

4.1 SYNNO Dissemination Plan

Publications: To enhance the quality of the planned publications, SYNNO will create graphic representations of information, such as infographics, overviews and explanatory images. Those visualisations will highlight and transport information to support the content and raise attention to the publication.

Besides, SYNNO will support the consortium in reviewing press releases or peer-reviewed publications (concerning a general perspective and the usage of project identity) if requested. SYNNO will raise awareness of the research outcomes and present the publications on various channels such as the project website, social media channels, newsletter, etc.

Dissemination at events: SYNNO is supporting the partners who are presenting the project on external events with DECICE presentations and print materials. SYNNO ensures the project identity of the DECICE Project by designing the online and offline materials. To attract attendees of the event, SYNNO provides DECICE roll-ups, posters, leaflets, folders, QR- Code posters, two kinds of stickers, etc. The different DECICE presentations can be shown either on a tablet or monitor at the booth or can be used for presentations in front of a bigger audience. On the DECICE website, designed and developed by SYNNO, attendees of the event can receive further information about the project. To keep interested people up to date SYNNO will highlight the DECICE newsletter as well as DECICE social media channels and motivate them to subscribe and follow. On the project website SYNNO has established an *EVENT* section where interesting events get presented. Therefore, SYNNO created an overview of topic related events, emphasised the events where DECICE will be presented and provides further information about events (co)-organised by DECICE.

Networking with other projects: SYNNO will support partners to present DECICE to other relevant projects with presentations and print materials using the project identity. Furthermore, SYNNO provides ongoing information about DECICE on channels like social media, the project website and newsletters which keeps other projects and interested parties updated. Aim of networking is to spread information about the project, share knowledge, plan co-organised events along with reaching out to the same audience together and create synergies beyond the funding period.

Events: In the context of dissemination of information about DECICE or the project's results, SYNNO plans to organise and carry out workshops, sessions or webinars. The aim is to promote DECICE, attract and interact with external stakeholders along with creating synergies. Besides that, SYNNO pursues sharing results and gaining insights as well as inducing interested organisations to exploit the project's solutions and outcomes. Furthermore, SYNNO will support the partners with the promotion of the

events to raise attention and reach a broad audience. Online or offline promotional materials will be designed by SYNNO to achieve the best results by addressing relevant stakeholders. The promotion of the events will be communicated through different channels like the DECICE project website, newsletter, social media channels, etc. to reach out to diverse target groups. If it comes to the events itself, SYNNO will set up the virtual events e.g., Webex call or will prepare and organise the physical event at a venue.

Videos: SYNNO will establish the official DECICE YouTube channel where the videos will be uploaded and described appropriately. The dissemination of the videos on several channels like website, social media, newsletter, events, etc. will be carried out by SYNNO as well. If required, SYNNO will support partners with the video creation. The aim of those videos is to introduce DECICE to a broader audience, disseminate information as well as results of DECICE and educate interested parties in this specific field. As videos have been proven to gain significant outreach and awareness, SYNNO will use this opportunity to encourage stakeholders' engagement.

Dissemination channels: To disseminate information about the project's outcomes effectively, SYNNO will apply a **multi-channel** dissemination approach. For this, the organisation will utilise the project website, newsletters and social media channels, including LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. The **project website** constitutes the project's main dissemination channel. As such it will be used by SYNNO to address a broad range of relevant stakeholders. Besides basic information about DECICE, such as background, objectives and project facts, the website provides regular project news and keeps interested parties informed on any planned workshops or webinars by DECICE in the event section. Furthermore, SYNNO uses **newsletters** to spread information, update on project results, send out Save the Dates or reminders for events, stay in contact with the stakeholders and much more. **LinkedIn and Twitter** represent great marketing and connection tools. By strategically utilising both platforms, SYNNO will seek to spread information about the project's achievements, increase the traffic on the project website and promote events. Moreover, SYNNO will utilise the project social media channels to build and sustain the involvement of external stakeholders in the various phases of project communication, motivate their participation and facilitate continuous knowledge exchange. During previous projects managed by SYNNO, **YouTube** has proven to be an effective dissemination channel to a vast audience of project stakeholders across Europe and beyond. Due to that, SYNNO will establish a YouTube channel and supports the video creation for introducing DECICE to a broader audience. Besides, those informative and educational videos will strengthen awareness and stakeholders' engagement.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: SYNNO will seek to engage with a number of different target groups like the industry and innovators, researcher and research institutes, other projects (related projects, RIAs, CSAs, etc.), standardisation bodies, European and international initiatives, policymakers, civil society, press, media, etc. To communicate effectively with these parties, SYNNO will seek to understand the challenges, which each of the stakeholders are facing and offer the project's outcomes as solutions to their needs.

4.2 UGOE Dissemination Plan

Publications: UGOE is planning to create two peer-reviewed papers in 2023.

- Literature survey scheduling algorithms on heterogeneous systems
- State-of-the-art scheduling strategies in Kubernetes

Dissemination at events: UGOE will attend the following events and present the DECICE project there.

- 2023: [ISC HPC](#) (IODC workshop)
- 2023: [KISSKI Symposium](#) (part of institution poster)

Networking with other projects: UGOE will network with other projects.

- Need to establish relationships in 2023
- The BMBF AI Service Centers: Hessian AI, KISSKI, ...

Events: UGOE will contribute to 2 events in total.

- *1 business models workshop (T6.1, M18-M24)*
 - Workshop about secure data processing with UMG
- *1 requirements workshop (T6.1, 2. in M7-M12)*
 - Will organize a public virtual workshop for the 2nd requirements workshop

Videos: UGOE has procured video equipment to be able to create videos. Planned videos:

- Explanation of a use case / prospect benefit for users
- Interview with contributors from UGOE

Dissemination channels: UGOE is disseminating content about DECICE via different channels.

- Dissemination on website: hps.vi4io.org

Stakeholder engagement and networks: UGOE will invite researchers and research institutions to DECICE workshops and present results of the project.

4.3 GWDG Dissemination Plan

Publications: GWDG plans one press release per year.

- 2023: contribution to Gauss Allianz Infobrief
- 2024: mid-term press release in GWDG newsletter
- 2025: press release at project end in GWDG newsletter

Dissemination at events: GWDG will attend the following event and present the DECICE project there.

- 2023: [ISC HPC](#) (NHR booth)

Networking with other projects: No comment.

Events: GWDG will contribute to 2 events in total.

- *1 co-organised webinars/workshops with other H2020 and/or HE funded projects (M1-M36)*
 - Co-Organization of the Huawei Kubernetes Workshop
- *1 final event for the presentation of the project results in collaboration with the other RIAs*
 - GWDG will organise the final event

Videos: GWDG will contribute to a video creation. Presentation of GWDG hardware infrastructure and discussion how DECICE could help managing the heterogeneous hardware.

Dissemination channels: GWDG will disseminate DECICE content via the following channels:

- GWDG social media channels: [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), Mastodon, [YouTube](#)
- GWDG blog: info.gwdg.de

Stakeholder engagement and networks: No comment.

4.4 E4 Dissemination Plan

Publications: E4 will publish a press release on DECICE goals and its involvement in the project, with the general aim to increase awareness on the project at a national level.

Dissemination at events: E4 is planning to present DECICE project at several external events, which will be constantly reported and updated in the shared file “Event Spreadsheet”. It is important to consider that many of the events indicated hereby are recurrent and that the E4’s participation is to be considered on an annual basis.

By now, the company Scientific Officer Daniele Gregori had the opportunity to present DECICE at the following conferences:

- [HPCAI Advisory Council](#), (Lugano, Switzerland, 3-5/04/2023).
- [Computing Frontiers 2023 Conference](#) (Bologna, Italy, 9-11/05/2023)
- International Supercomputing Conference ([ISC2023](#)) (Hannover, Germany, 22-25/05/2023), where E4 had a booth, showcase DECICE poster and give a speech on the project.
- [INFN Workshop sul Calcolo](#) (Savona, Italy, 22-26/05/2023)

Furthermore, DECICE will be presented at the following events:

- [PASC 2023](#) - Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing Conference (Davos, Switzerland, 26-28/06/2023)
- [HIPEACH 2024](#) (Munich, Germany, 17-19/01/2024)

Networking with other projects: E4 is involved as a Partner in several projects funded by the European Commission, in particular under [EuroHPC Joint Undertaking](#). With the overall aim to create synergies among different projects sharing similar topics, we will consider the opportunity to network with other projects by acting as a *trait d’union*.

Events: Given the significant contribution to dissemination activities at external events, E4 is not planning to contribute to the organisation of internal project events, such as workshops or webinars. However, we will provide our contribution in terms of content creation and presentation of the WP/Tasks E4 is leading, for example on the occasion of the final event and, in general, when specifically required.

Videos: E4 will support the Communication leader in increasing the visibility of the project videos by sharing them, once they are published on official DECICE channels. E4 will repost videos on the company’s website and social media pages (LinkedIn and YouTube).

Dissemination channels: Information on the project’s main results and outcomes will be disseminated by E4 on two different channels: the [company website](#) and official [LinkedIn page](#).

First, E4 will create a specific section devoted to DECICE project on a specific website page where all European projects in which the company is currently involved are listed. The section will include the project logo, a short description of its main goals and the role of E4, and a direct link to DECICE website. Furthermore, at least one article will be published on E4 “News / Blog” section on the website.

Secondly, E4 will also share posts on its official LinkedIn page featuring significant updates on DECICE: e.g., posts published on the project’ social media pages will be reshared and contextualised, as well

as original posts in case of important updates involving E4 role and/or the participation to international events and conferences where DECICE project was presented.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: E4 will disseminate DECICE main results and promote the project activities among its network of contacts, especially in the corporate/industrial environment, Universities, and research centres.

4.5 KTH Dissemination Plan

Publications: KTH plans to be involved in at least 2 peer-review publications and will furthermore seek for opportunities to report about DECICE results in other forms, e.g., blog posts, white papers.

Dissemination at events: KTH will use all suitable events, where its team is involved, to provide information about the DECICE project and report results. This includes, in particular, HPC conferences like [ISC](#) and [SC](#) as well as events like the [EuroHPC Summit](#). The organisers of ISC and the EuroHPC Summit regularly offer the opportunity to submit project posters. We expect that the growing interest in the compute continuum topic to result in various efforts to organise “birds of a feather” (BoF) sessions and workshops during HPC conferences like ISC and SC, which we will support either as co-organiser or contributor.

Networking with other projects: KTH is involved in different EC-funded projects where the results of DECICE can be disseminated. Furthermore, KTH will leverage its involvement in relevant organisations like [ETP4HPC](#).

Events: The KTH team will involve itself in the business model and requirements workshops, actively contribute to the final event, be available for contributions to the training efforts and the foreseen webinars.

Videos: KTH will contribute to the creation of videos foreseen in the project plan.

Dissemination channels: No comment.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: KTH will leverage its network within the HPC community to communicate about DECICE and disseminate its results. For instance, KTH will feed project results in [ETP4HPC](#)'s technical work, e.g., the writing of future Strategic Research Agendas.

4.6 USTUTT Dissemination Plan

Publications: As a technical partner, USTUTT will contribute to any publications that disseminate the results of DECICE and which are relevant to USTUTT's tasks and expertise. Topics could include the realization of continuous integration and continuous deployment (e.g., as a white paper for best practices) or the implementation of an AI training pipeline across heterogeneous infrastructures including HPC, Cloud, and Edge.

When it comes to dissemination of the objectives, activities and results of DECICE to the general public, USTUTT has already started with some actions. For example, a news article about DECICE was published, and USTUTT spread knowledge about DECICE on its social media channels ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#)). This will continue throughout the project's runtime. Furthermore, DECICE will be acknowledged in the upcoming annual report of HLRS (print) to be published in May 2023.

Dissemination at events: A project leaflet is prepared by USTUTT to be handed out to interested visitors at conferences, workshops and events in general. The next major conferences where USTUTT is present with a dedicated booth are the [International Supercomputing Conference \(ISC\)](#) in Hamburg in May 2023, and the [Supercomputing Conference \(SC\)](#) in November 2023. At the ISC23, USTUTT will participate in the annual High-Performance Container Workshop to talk about how HPC centres support the usage and deployment of containers; this is relevant to DECICE and thus there is the opportunity to bring into the discussions DECICE as a case study.

In general, USTUTT will participate and disseminate information about DECICE throughout the runtime of the project at other relevant events, too.

Networking with other projects: USTUTT is coordinating the European projects EuroCC2 and CASTIEL2 to establish national competence centres for HPC and related topics across Europe and their interaction. In this context, a common strategy for continuous integration and continuous deployment will be developed for the [EuroHPC JU](#) supercomputers to harmonize access to those systems. This is strongly related to the activities in DECICE, and thus a regular knowledge exchange about best practices has already started.

In future, it could become relevant to reach out to [Gaia-X](#)-focused projects including [Gaia-X4ICM](#) (a German project to enable production environments to leverage Gaia-X) and [InHPC-DE](#) (a joint project of all three national HPC centres to set up a Gaia-X ecosystem close to high-performance computing infrastructures). Since USTUTT is indirectly through the Gauss Centre for Supercomputing member of Gaia-X, close ties already exist and can be exploited when needed.

Events: USTUTT will contribute its knowledge and expertise to any webinar, workshop or training whenever it is required. This will likely happen in the context of joint, co-organised webinars and workshops and training workshops, as well as of course any joint dissemination events that require participation of all project partners.

Videos: Nothing is planned at the given time.

Dissemination channels: USTUTT is actively serving the following channels with new content:

- LinkedIn: [@HLRS - High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart](#)
- Twitter: [@HLRS_HPC](#)
- Website: www.hlrs.de

Those channels are also used to disseminate any information related to DECICE.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: USTUTT is involved in several communities and networks. Of particular interest is for sure the community around the national competence centres (NCCs) that were formed across Europe under the [EuroCC](#) initiative. The network is composed of research institutes, SMEs and industry players interested in HPC, Cloud and novel technologies such as quantum computing from all European countries. Thus, there will be a chance to disseminate project results to those channels or announce events.

4.7 HWDU Dissemination Plan

Publications: Once the DECICE API is more mature, we plan to conduct several experiments on our own hardware that will eventually be published in a peer-reviewed paper.

Dissemination at events: We plan to disseminate the project at [KubeCon](#) and possibly at the [ISC-HPC conference](#) every year.

Networking with other projects: No comment.

Events:

- We plan to organise one OEHI-DECICIE workshop per year in combination with the OEHI consortium.
- We plan to organise one webinar per year around DECICE.

Videos: No comment.

Dissemination channels: No comment.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: No comment.

4.8 FBU Dissemination Plan

Publications: FBU has published a [Press Release in April 2023](#) to raise the awareness of general-purpose media about DECICE project. The second Press Release is planned for the period after the project is completed.

Together with other partners, FBU has developed a scientific publication that will be presented at the [ACM Computing Frontiers conference](#) in May 2023. FBU intends to develop one scientific publication per year during the project implementation.

Dissemination at events: FBU is [HiPEAC](#) member, and we would like to present DECICE at one of the HiPEAC events.

Networking with other projects: FBU is maintaining the contact with other related European projects via [EUCloudEdgeIoT](#) initiative. In this context, DECICE is invited to participate in "[Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT](#)" event in May, Brussels.

Events: FBU is leading the WP2 that focuses on AI-enabled scheduling and optimization of computing continuum. We will present WP2 in future DECICE events (workshops / webinars). Furthermore, we are looking forward to organising a joint workshop with related HE projects at one of the upcoming [HiPEAC conferences](#).

Videos: FBU will contribute to a DECICE video by describing the results of WP2.

Dissemination channels: We are using the website of FBU to distribute the key information about DECICE. Furthermore, scientists at FBU are using their personal Twitter accounts to disseminate information about DECICE.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: FBU is planning to use [HiPEAC](#) and [EUCloudEdgeIoT](#) for stakeholder engagement and interaction with other related projects.

4.9 TOP-IX Dissemination Plan

Publications: No comment.

Dissemination at events: No comment.

Networking with other projects: TOP-IX can explore contamination and cross-collaboration with [FLUIDOS](#) project. FLUIDOS (Flexible, scaLable, secUre, and decentralised Operating System) aims to leverage the enormous, unused processing capacity at the edge, scattered across heterogeneous edge devices that struggle to integrate with each other and to coherently form a seamless computing continuum.

FLUIDOS is funded by Horizon Europe - <https://www.fluidos.eu/>

TOP-IX is involved in the Project Consortium and will be working on the prototyping of a broker. The FLUIDOS nodes delegate to the broker the aggregation and control of heterogeneous resources (e.g., CPU, storage).

Events: TOP-IX will organize an internal workshop to collect DECICE use-cases requirements. It will be a collaborative online session involving use case owners.

If needed, TOP-IX is available to co-organize also a public online webinar/workshop to present use cases (particularly the result of requirements collection) to all the Project partners. This event can be open to a wider public.

Videos: No comment.

Dissemination channels: TOP-IX main website (www.top-ix.org), DECICE project presentation and main update can be delivered on this channel.

TOP-IX social media channels ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#) mainly): they can be used to repost DECICE news and updates or provide additional information about status of work.

TOP-IX Medium channel (<https://medium.com/topixlab>): this media is available to present main achievements or to share relevant knowledges acquired during the project.

TOP-IX Newsletter: used for communication to TOP-IX Consortium members.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: TOP-IX dissemination activities will reach a wide network of Italian stakeholders: SMEs, large Corporates and Public Administrations. The main targets of TOP-IX communication are the TOP-IX Consortium Members (90+) in the field of Telecommunication and Networking, Internet Service Providers, Connectivity providers and tech stakeholders. TOP-IX is also part of some relevant international networks:

- [BDVA, Big Data Value Association](#)
- [GAIA X](#)
- [IDSA, International Data Space Association](#)
- [EURO-IX](#)

4.10 UNIBO Dissemination Plan

Publications: UNIBO is planning to contribute to this objective by publishing the research outcome in ML models for the creation of digital twins for the computing continuum, datasets for the training of those ML models, and computing continuum pipelines for drone-based environmental monitoring.

Dissemination at events: UNIBO is planning to contribute to the dissemination of the DECICE results in conferences and workshops in the computing continuum community as well as to industrial partners.

Networking with other projects: UNIBO is a member of the [HiPEAC](#) network, and also a partner of the [EPI SGA2](#), and several [EuroHPC](#) projects, like [EUPEX](#), [REGALE](#). It is also a partner of the HPC national centre funded in the recovery plan program. It is also a partner of the [ISOLDE](#) and [TRISTAN KDT](#) projects.

Events: UNIBO is planning to contribute to the workshop and training events.

Videos: UNIBO is planning to work with partner on video on demonstrating the technology developed in the project.

Dissemination channels: UNIBO is planning to disseminate DECICE results with scientific publications and by participating to relevant conferences and workshops.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: UNIBO is planning to engage with researchers in the fields of the HPC and computing continuum, as well as with companies involved in creating solutions for the use of HPC and edge technologies for environmental monitoring.

4.11 MARUN Dissemination Plan

Publications: MarUn plans to publish at least 2 peer-reviewed publication, related to studies conducted by MarUn in DECICE project.

Dissemination at events: During the DECICE project timespan, MarUn will host 2 annual workshops that have been previously organized with the names:

- [“From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop”](#)
- [“2nd From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop”](#)

The workshops focused on the aspects of intelligent transportation systems including autonomous and connected mobility, cloud systems in intelligent mobility, and automotive systems security where the target audience of these events was public/industry organizations in the automotive and telecommunications domain and OEMs. Oncoming events are planned to be held on similar topics with an additional focus on the Internet of Things and the cloud ecosystem. The workshops will leverage the activities and results of the DECICE project through visual and aural tools.

Networking with other projects: MarUn can disseminate and utilize the tools and results of the project DECICE in several contributed projects. These projects are:

- [BRIGHTER](#) - Breakthrough in micro-bolometer imaging (Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)
- [LoLiPoP IoT](#) (Long Life Power Platforms for Internet of Things)(Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)

MarUn collaborates in these projects in 3 different use cases that accommodate cloud-edge collaboration in their lifecycle in the long-term. The DECICE framework is an appropriate tool to implement the use cases. Therefore, MarUn can encourage using it during or after the projects, where the outputs of these projects will be in deployment.

Events: MarUn can contribute to co-organized webinars/workshops by presenting and demonstrating the use of the DECICE framework in the use case that it is leading. MarUn can also contribute to the final event by physically demonstrating the use case.

Videos: MarUn will prepare at least one video regarding the project results and their implementation in real-world scenarios.

Dissemination channels: MarUn will disseminate information regarding the DECICE project using VeNIT Lab's social media channels on LinkedIn, [Twitter](#), and [Instagram](#). These will include the R&D activities carried out and the events contributed by MarUn in the context of the DECICE project, with necessary references to the project's website and social media accounts.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: MarUn will seek ways of exploiting the results with its industrial partners consisting of OEMs, technology, and service providers in various domains that include smart mobility, automotive and smart manufacturing. The dissemination will be visible to industrial organizations from various domains, which are in the communication range of MarUn. These include national and international service providers, public organizations, R&D organizations, manufacturers, and OEMs.

4.12 BIGTRI Dissemination Plan

Publications: BigTRI plans to publish 1 conference or journal publication during the DECICE project.

Dissemination at events: BigTRI closely collaborates with Marmara University on arranging annual workshops previously held two times with the name "From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop" (["From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop"](#)) and "[2nd From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop"](#)"). The workshops hosted many stakeholders in the industry in automotive, smart mobility, and telecommunications domains. During the project, Marmara University plans to arrange two of these workshops to be held annually. BigTRI will contribute to these as a speaker and organizer. The DECICE project and its outputs will be disseminated during these events.

Networking with other projects: The projects that BigTRI collaborates at the same time with the DECICE project are:

- [BRIGHTER](#) - Breakthrough in micro-bolometer imaging (Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)
- [LoLiPoP IoT](#) (Long Life Power Platforms for Internet of Things) (Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)

BigTRI will explore the ways for disseminating and exploiting the project's results in the use cases it collaborates. The projects' consortia accommodate various types of companies and research organizations from different domains in which exploiting the results in the use cases will accelerate the penetration of the project's results in the industry.

Events: BigTRI can contribute to co-organized webinars and the final event to present the use case it contributes to and demonstrate the results.

Videos: No comment.

Dissemination channels: BigTRI plans to utilize its social media platforms on LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram to share information about the DECICE project. This will involve highlighting BigTRI's research and development efforts and events related to the project, while also providing references to the project.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: BigTRI intends to collaborate with its industrial partners, who are OEMs, technology providers, and service providers in fields such as smart mobility, automotive, and smart manufacturing, to explore opportunities for utilizing the outcomes of the project. The dissemination of the results will be accessible to industrial organizations within BigTRI's

communication network, including national and international service providers, public organizations, R&D institutions, manufacturers, and OEMs from various domains.

4.13 NAG Dissemination Plan

Publications: NAG raises awareness of significant research outcomes and present the publications on various channels such as on the NAG [website](#), social media channels ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#)), newsletter, etc. if appropriate. Together with all partners, NAG contributes news articles for the DECICE website.

Dissemination at events: NAG will do dissemination at events. The exact events will be communicated as soon as decided internally. When planned, any assets will be displayed at the NAG booth (roll-ups/posters/leaflets) or on-screen with a PowerPoint presentation slide.

Networking with other projects: NAG is not involved in any other projects.

Events: NAG will contribute in all events organised by DECICE. (

Videos: There is no budget or plan to produce any videos in relation to the DECICE project at present. NAG will be open to sharing video content produced by SYNYO.

Dissemination channels: Any dissemination from NAG will be included in our [website Blog](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#). It may also be cascaded in an internal newsletter.

The NAG blog will be used to provide the main content and information on the project to users. It will also link to the project website and be used to provide a customer journey that will encourage engagement.

The NAG LinkedIn will be the main NAG Social Media channel used for DECICE dissemination. NAG will link from LinkedIn to the NAG blog site, which in turn will link to the project site. NAG may also do 'lite' LinkedIn posts that talk to NAGs involvement in the project and provide a link directly to the DECICE project website.

Twitter is less utilised by NAG, but posts will be reposted from NAG LinkedIn to Twitter, adjusted to fit.

The Marketing Department at NAG is working on an internal Newsletter. If this is complete, DECICE project updates will be communicated in there periodically.

Stakeholder engagement and networks: NAG's work will be focused more on the internal stakeholders of the project.

5. Dissemination Materials

This chapter outlines the materials that will be used and the dissemination activities that will be conducted to deliver the relevant project information to the audience.

5.1 Visual Design Concept

Central to the communication and dissemination activities and materials is a uniform and aesthetically pleasing project identity reflected through the strategically selected naming, logo, fonts, typography, layout colour scheme, key visuals and the DECICE design in general. In the following chapter the visual design concept is presented in more detail.

The project identity is crucial for the creation of print materials and screen designs to ensure the brand recognition.

5.2 Colour Scheme

One of the most important determinants influencing perception in branding and advertising is colour. When selecting a colour, it is important to understand that colours have different meanings and symbolism across countries and cultures. With regards to the positioning of DECICE, we decided to use two colours which are close on the colour wheel, namely blue and violet. The colour blue is very commonly used in combination with any shade of purple. Creativity as meaning of violet and the thoughtful calm of the shades of blue are a perfect mix and gives the DECICE colour scheme (cf Fig. 1) its balance. [1] In addition, blue is associated with security, reliability, technology, trustworthiness and therefore often used in corporate or cybersecurity matters. [2] Another advantage of this colour pattern and the decisive factor for selecting it were the positive connotations of blue in the Western and European world: trust, business, as well as truth, responsibility, fidelity and serenity. Besides, in the western civilisation both blue and purple stand for authority and calm. [3]

More detailed meaning of the colours used for DECICE are presented below.

Shades of Blue

Blue as nature's colour for water and sky is the favourite colour of all people. It is the most complex of all colours and convey a sense of cool, understanding, loyalty, trust, and cleanliness. The different shades of blue provide a broad variety of meaning as shown in figure 1. [4]

Purple/Violet

Purple gets generated through combining two opposite colours on the colour wheel, hot red and cool blue. For DECICE cool blue-purple/violet, a shade of purple with more blue colour than red, was chosen to match the other blue tones in the DECICE colour scheme.

Due to its rare appearance in nature, purple was associated with nobility and luxury in earlier times.[5] Nowadays purple symbolises creativity and independent thinking. [6]

CMYK: 100/40/0/56
RGB: 57/75/116
Hex: #394b74

Dark blue: Intelligence, trust, authority, dignity, cool. Because of its meaning, dark blue is commonly used for business and corporate identity. [4]

CMYK: 75/11/0/0
RGB: 90/185/234
Hex: #5ab9ea

Light blue | sky: Infinity, peace, ethereal, serenity, spiritual [4]

CMYK: 81/47/0/0
RGB: 86/128/233
Hex: #5680e9

CMYK: 64/68/0/0
RGB: 136/96/208
Hex: #8860d0

Bright blue | ocean, water: Strength, dependability, coolness, cleanliness [4]

Dark purple/violet: creativity, intellectual, innovation, sophistication [5]

Figure 1: DECICE Colour Scheme and Meaning

5.3 Logo

Out of 13 logo drafts, three have been pre-selected internally and subsequently rated by the consortium via **logo poll** (cf Fig. 2). Finally, the DECICE colour scheme was integrated in the **chosen DECICE logo** and negative versions of the logo in black and white were created. Of course, the final DECICE logo was adapted as well to different use-case specific versions and application scenarios. Additionally, to the logo, an icon/favicon was created (cf Fig. 3). Starting with the colour scheme and logo, the project identity was complemented by appealing fonts. More details can be found under 5.4 Identity Kit.

5.3.1 Logo Poll

Figure 2: DECICE Logo Poll

5.3.2 DECICE Final Logo, Icon and Favicon

Figure 3: DECICE Final Logo, Icon and Favicon

5.3.3 Meaning of the DECICE Logo

The DECICE logo combines elements that represent the project's focus on intelligent collaboration in the Device-Edge-Cloud framework. The logo design prominently features the project name, "DECICE," with careful attention given to the typography. The letterforms are clean, modern, and easily legible, conveying professionalism and clarity.

The central icon of the logo is a digital cloud, symbolising the project's connection to cloud computing and data management. The cloud is depicted in a stylised and sleek manner, with smooth curves and a sense of depth. It represents the storage, processing, and distribution of data in the context of the Device-Edge-Cloud framework.

To align with the desired colour scheme, the logo primarily utilises shades of blue and purple. The use of blue symbolises trust, reliability, and technology, while purple represents creativity, innovation, and sophistication. The combination of these colours creates a harmonious and modern visual identity for the DECICE project.

Overall, the DECICE logo conveys a professional and innovative image, capturing the essence of the project's objectives in the Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration Framework. It communicates the project's focus on intelligent connectivity, data management, and collaboration while maintaining a visually appealing and memorable design.

5.4 Identity Kit

In the first month of the project SYNYO focused on creating all relevant reference documents (e.g., deliverable and presentation templates) and developing the project identity including the logo, colour scheme, fonts and all basic designs for communication and dissemination such as print materials and screen designs. Examples for print materials are leaflets, posters, folders, roll-ups, business cards, stickers etc. Designs for online usage were needed for the social media accounts like banners and post templates, website design and a power point presentation template for the consortium.

This project identity kit includes all the required elements for project communication and dissemination available in one place, and allows to easily present the project, its aims, activities and results in different contexts.

Identity Overview

The identity overview (cf Fig. 4) is the essential part in the identity kit and provides the consortium with all necessary design information. Reaching from the DECICE logos and their proper use, colours and fonts.

Figure 4: DECICE Identity Overview

5.5. Key Visuals

To represent the project and the related topic, the following key visuals (cf Fig. 5) have been established. For the following isometric images, the project identity colours were chosen to ensure one uniform project design. The key visuals embody the DECICE content and support the reader to quickly understand the topic. Images were provided by Shutterstock under the standard licence and adapted to the DECICE project identity.

Figure 5: DECICE Key Visuals

5.6 Print Materials

Experienced graphic designers at SYNNO created all print materials ensuring the project identity. In addition to the visual design, the focus was laid on high quality material with a good value for money. To promote the project, several print materials have been created. Those diverse print materials, such as leaflets, folders, business cards and stickers can be distributed for example during events. Furthermore, roll-up and poster attract interested parties and provide a good insight on the DECICE project.

The print materials have been distributed to all consortium partners in digital form, are available on the website *MEDIA* page ready to download and can be distributed in printed form if required so that print materials can be handed out at events or conferences to interested stakeholders.

5.6.1 Leaflet

The attention drawing DECICE leaflet (cf Fig. 6 and 7), provides a brief overview of the topic, the project objectives, project facts, consortium and the communication channels. The brand identity is visualised using the brand colours, brand images and the logo. The shiny A5 leaflet with thick paper provides a high quality optic and haptic. This handy format is printed on both sides. The front page looks appealing and offers basics like the topic, contact and the logo. Additional information such as the above mentioned basic project information can be found at the back of the DECICE Leaflet.

Figure 6: DECICE Leaflet Front/Back

Figure 7: DECICE Leaflet Front/Back Mock-Up

5.6.2 Folder

The DECICE folder (cf Fig. 8 and 9) in A4 is the perfect companion for events and fairs to collect paper material. Just like the leaflet, the folder attracts with a shiny optic and high quality haptic in project identity design. Matching to the leaflet, the front page provides all basic information. On the back the EU and partner logos are shown and the contact possibilities like, website, mail, Twitter and LinkedIn are highlighted.

Figure 8: DECICE Folder Front/Back

Figure 9: DECICE Folder Front/Back Mock-Up

5.6.3 Roll-Up

In line with the other print materials, the roll-up (cf Fig. 10 and 11) presents the topic of the project, the contact information and the consortium ensuring the project identity. The prominent logo and eye-catching image alongside the contrast of blue and white ensures attention at events from even far away. Additionally, to a clean roll-up with the focus on the image and logo, another roll-up with more content like a brief description of the topic, project objectives, contacts & facts was created. Especially for short presentations at event booths, this roll-up helps to provide an aesthetically pleasing overview of the DECICE project.

Figure 10: DECICE Roll-Ups

Figure 11: DECICE Roll-Ups Mock-Ups

5.6.4 Business Cards

This shiny business card (cf Fig. 12 and 13) in project identity design serves as a cue validity. The front attracts with a clean project identity design and DECICE logo, while the back presents all DECICE channels like the project website, mail-address, LinkedIn account and Twitter account. The outstanding QR code on the white background raises awareness and is a direct call to action. It links to the website for more information. Additionally, interested parties can subscribe to the newsletter to stay informed about updates, events and project results.

Figure 12: DECICE Business Cards

Figure 13: DECICE Business Cards Mock-Up

5.6.5 Stickers

SYNYO created two kinds of DECICE stickers (cf Fig. 14 and 15). One looking like the logo and the other like the DECICE icon. Those stickers can be stuck on to laptops, notepads, smartphone cases, cupboards. Especially on events, stickers are always nice as give away. At the same time the stickers are an easy way for consortium members to associate with the project through the stickers and identify with it.

Figure 14: DECICE Sticker – Logo

Figure 15: DECICE Sticker – Icon

5.7 Screen Design

In addition to the print materials SYNYO created a screen design using the project identity design.

5.7.1 Social Media Banners

This simple but distinct social media banner (cf Fig. 16) in project identity design provides the project topic and typically DECICE image. The following Icon (cf Fig. 17) is used on Twitter and LinkedIn and represents DECICE.

Figure 16: DECICE Social Media Banner

Figure 17: DECICE Social Media Profile Image

5.7.2 Social Media Post Templates

To ensure the project identity throughout all social media posts, templates (cf Fig. 18) had been created for different kinds of information. Two of many different templates are shown below.

Figure 18: DECICE Social Media Post Templates

5.7.3 PowerPoint Template

To ensure a coherent identity of presentations about the DECICE project at events and conferences, a presentation template (cf Fig. 19 and 20) has been designed and represents the project identity. It includes a variety of different types of slides which reflect the project’s colours and visual identity.

Figure 19: DECICE Presentation Template

Figure 20: DECICE Presentation Template Mock-Up

Furthermore, some presentations with basic information about the DECICE project have been created to ensure a uniform representation. Those presentations are available with different number of pages. One of the presentations can be found below (cf Fig. 21).

Figure 21: DECICE Presentation Content Template

6. Channels and Online Presence

To ensure the outreach to stakeholders and the general public with relevant information about the DECICE project as well as regular updates on its progress, several communication and dissemination channels and activities have been established. The different means of communication include the DECICE project website, the project's social media channels, news articles published on the project website, conferences and events, workshops, and the DECICE newsletter. Using these means, DECICE will ensure the constant communication with stakeholders as well as the successful dissemination of project results.

6.1 DECICE Project Website

As explained in detail in the Deliverable D6.3 Online and Media Presence, the project website is the central tool for keeping the stakeholders and public informed about the DECICE project. The website is available via <https://www.decice.eu/> and has been launched at the beginning of the project. Activity on the project website is continuously being monitored via Google Analytics. In October 2024 (M24) an insight analysis will be provided in the update of this Deliverable.

Its main goal is to promote and disseminate the project, its objectives and its results.

On the *HOME* page, users can find a brief description about the project, an overview of the project's objectives, latest DECICE news articles, Twitter news and the consortium partners as well as a link to the newsletter subscription form. Subpages of the project website include the following:

- A *NEWS* page where the consortium regularly posts articles about relevant milestones and related topics;
- An *EVENTS* page that provides an overview over events (content related, DECICE attending, (co)-organised by DECICE).
- An *ABOUT* page containing the project background, important facts and information about DECICE, the project concept, the project impacts as well as the project structure including the work packages and access to public deliverables;
- A *CONSORTIUM* page where all partners are being presented;
- A *MEDIA* page providing downloads of the DECICE print materials, presentations, logos etc.;
- A *CONTACT* page including the project's contact information and a contact form.

Figure 22: DECICE Project Website

6.2 Social Media

To maximise awareness about the DECICE project and enable two-way-communication with stakeholders, a Twitter and a LinkedIn account have been set up and are being operated by SYNNO GmbH. A YouTube channel will be set up if necessary for videos created by DECICE partners. On the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, regular updates on the project's progress, information about events, and other relevant information since the start of the project are posted. All partners contribute by creating content for those two channels. Furthermore, the partners support the growth of those communication channels by either sharing, liking, subscribing, following, engaging or posting regularly. Apart from raising awareness of the project, social media is an important way of establishing connections with people and organisations in the field, building networks and laying the ground for future collaborations. Please find more information about the DECICE social media channels in the D6.3 "Establish an Online & Media Presence".

DECICE

@DECICE_EU

Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration Framework

🇪🇺 Funded by @HorizonEU (GA ID: 101092582)
#deciceEU #Cloud, #IoT #AI #DigitalTwin #CognitiveCloud

🔗 decice.eu 📅 Joined December 2022

202 Following 104 Followers

Figure 23: DECICE Social Media - Twitter

Figure 24: DECICE Social Media - LinkedIn

Activity and interactions on the project’s social media accounts are being monitored through built-in analytics tools as well as manual documentation. The two channels have experienced a steady growth in followers since the start of the project. A detailed look into the analytics of the DECICE social media channels will be offered in the D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan Update in October 2024 (M24).

6.3 News Articles

To offer more detailed information about relevant progress of the project as well as information about related topics, articles are regularly being published on the DECICE project website. These articles contain information about project milestones, progress updates, events, or general information on topics in the same field. Each consortium partner is expected to provide a news article as scheduled. This new content on the DECICE website about the project and related information helps to achieve our KPIs concerning website views and supports to be rated better by Google. [7]

Figure 25: DECICE News Articles

6.4 Newsletter

The DECICE newsletter has been created to offer regular updates about events and the project’s progress to interested stakeholders. The sign-up form can be found on the *HOME* page, *NEWS* page and in the footer. The newsletter will be sent out at least three times a year and provides updates about the project’s progress, events, and opportunities for involvement.

7. Dissemination Activities

In the following section, past and planned dissemination activities by the DECICE consortium will be presented. These activities aim to raise awareness about the project and maximise its impact.

7.1 Events

The consortium partners plan to attend a broad variety of events representative for the cloud computing industry to present the DECICE project and its results. Furthermore, networking and cooperation with other EU-project will get accelerated.

In the D6.1 Update in M24, more events (co)-organised by DECICE will be presented in detail. Several training workshops and hackathons will be organized that illustrate how to use the DECICE solution. The organization and implementation of a final networking event will be the biggest of the planned events and will present the results and use cases in collaboration with the other RIAs. It will bring together members of the consortium, expert and advisory board, representatives of the R&D community, industry organizations and decision makers. Furthermore, the event will be an adequate forum to discuss the conclusions of DECICE and ensure its sustainable exploitation beyond the funding period.

7.1.1 Participation in Past Events

Since the start of the project, members of the DECICE consortium have been participating in various conferences and workshops, where the project and its aims were presented to stakeholders such as industry, researchers and other relevant target groups. Participation in these events facilitated networking, communication and dissemination with and among stakeholders in the project field. Even more important, the DECICE project has been presented to raise awareness. The following table presents the events where DECICE has been represented by consortium partners. The events are listed chronologically to provide a clear overview of the dissemination activities that have been carried out so far with the aim to raise awareness and maximise the project's impact.

Table 4: Past Events Organised or Attended

DECICE Partner	Date	Event Name	Location	Type of Activity
All Partners	2023-11-17	Kick Off Meeting	Online	Kick Off Meeting
UGOE	2023-01-16	Secure Data Processing	Germany	Presentation of the DECICE project
FBU	2023-01-30	Horizon Europe Info Day	Online	Presentation of the DECICE project
E4	2023-02-09–2023-02-11	WAICF - World AI Cannes Festival 2023	France (Cannes)	Presentation of the DECICE project
KTH, E4	2023-03-20–2023-03-	EuroHPC Summit 2023	Sweden (Gothenburg)	Presentation of the DECICE project

	23)	
UGOE	2023-03-21–2023-03-23	KISSKI Symposium	Germany (Göttingen)	Presentation of the DECICE project
All Partners	2023-03-28–2023-03-29	Kick Off Meeting	Germany (Göttingen)	Kick Off Meeting
E4	2023-04-03–2023-04-06	HPCAI Advisory Council	Swiss (Lugano)	Presentation of the DECICE project
HWDU	2023-04-18–2023-04-21	KubeCon 2023	Netherlands (Amsterdam)	Presentation of the DECICE project
SYNYO, TOP-IX, E4, NAG, MarUn, GWDG, UNIBO, UGOE	2023-04-20	DECICE Use Case Requirements Workshop	Online	Workshop organised by DECICE (TOP-IX, SYNYO)
UNIBO, E4	2023-05-09–2023-05-11	CF2023 (ACM Computing Frontiers conference)	Italy (Bologna)	Presentation of the DECICE project
E4, KTH, USTUTT, UGOE, GWDG, NAG	2023-05-21–2023-05-25	ISC HPC 2023	Germany (Hamburg)	Presentation of the DECICE project
E4	2023-05-22–2023-05-26	INFN Workshop sul Calcolo	Italy (Savona)	Presentation of the DECICE project

7.1.2 Participation in Future Events

To gain outreach and optimize communication with stakeholders and representatives from all relevant areas, DECICE consortium partners will continuously attend relevant events and will present the project. The following table shows a collection of events identified as relevant where the attendance of consortium partners is planned. As the project progresses, further events and conferences will be added to this list.

Table 5: Future Events to be Organised or Attended

DECICE Partner	Date	Event Name	Location	Type of Activity
E4	2023-06-	PASC23	Switzerland	Presentation of

	26–2023-06-28		(Davos)	the DECICE project
USTUTT KTH (FBU)	2023-11-12–2023-11-13	SC23 (Supercomputing Conference) Workshops	USA (Denver)	Presentation of the DECICE project
E4, FBU	2024-01-17–2024-01-19	HIPEAC 2024	Germany (Munich)	Presentation of the DECICE project
(E4)	2024-02-08–2024-02-10	WAICF - World AI Cannes Festival 2023	France (Cannes)	Presentation of the DECICE project
MARUN BIGTRI	TBA	From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop	Turkey (Istanbul)	Presentation of the DECICE project
MARUN BIGTRI	TBA	2nd From Connected to Autonomous Cars: Intelligent Transportation Systems Workshop	Turkey (Istanbul)	Presentation of the DECICE project

7.2 Publications

To ensure the presentation of the project's results to the scientific community, the DECICE consortium aims to publish at least five press releases or peer-reviewed publications. The following table provides an overview of already released publications as well as a list of planned publications by the consortium partners.

Table 6: Publication Overview

Partner	Publication Typ	Title	Description	Status
FBU	Press Release	DECICE: Cloud-Management mithilfe von Künstlicher Intelligenz	FBU Press Release about FBU and the DECICE project	Done
All Partners	Invited Paper/ Scientific Publication	DECICE: Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration Framework	Invited Paper at the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers 2023	Done
UGOE	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Literature survey scheduling algorithms on heterogeneous systems	Tba	Planned
UGOE	Peer-	State-of-the-art	Tba	Planned

	Reviewed Publication	scheduling strategies in Kubernetes		
GWDG	Article	Tba	2023 – contribution to Gauss Allianz Infobrief	Planned
GWDG	Press Release	Tba	2024 – mid-term press release in GWDG newsletter	Planned
GWDG	Press Release	Tba	2025 – press release at project end in GWDG newsletter	Planned
E4	Press Release	Tba	DECICE goals, E4 involvement - awareness on national level	Planned
KTH	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	Tba	Planned
KTH	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	Tba	Planned
KTH	Blog Post, White Paper	Tba	Report about DECICE results in other forms	Planned
USTUTT	White Paper	Possible Topic: The realization of continuous integration and continuous deployment	As a technical partner, USTUTT will contribute to any publications that disseminate the results of DECICE and which are relevant to USTUTT's tasks and expertise.	Planned
USTUTT	Tba	Possible Topic: The implementation of an AI training pipeline across heterogeneous infrastructures including HPC, Cloud, and Edge	As a technical partner, USTUTT will contribute to any publications that disseminate the results of DECICE and which are relevant to USTUTT's tasks and expertise.	Planned
USTUTT	Report	Tba	Annual report of HLRs (print, May 2023)	Planned
HWDU	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	About experiments of DECICE API on Huawei Hardware	Planned

FBU	Press Release	Tba	At the end of the project	Planned
UNIBO	Tba	Tba	Research outcome	Planned
MARUN	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	Tba	Planned
MARUN	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	Tba	Planned
BIGTRI	Peer-Reviewed Publication	Tba	Conference or journal publication	Planned

7.3 EU-funded Projects and Organisations

The DECICE project lays a high focus on organising events, networking and raising awareness of the project. DECICE plans to co-organise six events like webinars or workshops with other H2020 or HE funded projects. The table further displays other projects and organisations identified for potential collaborations such as by co-organising events, or for dissemination. The mentioned consortium partner below is either already in contact or plans to contact the project or organisation.

Table 7: Projects/Organisations Identified for Potential Collaboration and Dissemination

Partner	Title	Topic
UGOE	Hessian AI	The Hessian Center for Artificial Intelligence
UGOE	KISSKI Symposium	Service Center for AI (sensitive & critical infrastructure)
KTH	ETP4HPC	European technology platform for high performance computing: Industry-led think-tank promoting European HPC research and innovation to support Europe's competitiveness
USTUTT	EuroCC2	The National Competence Centres (NCCs) are the central points of contact for HPC and related technologies in their country.
USTUTT	CASTIEL2	Promotes interaction and exchange of expertise and competence across the NCC network.
USTUTT, E4, KTH, UNIBO	EuroHPC JU	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)
USTUTT	Gaia-X4ICM	A German project to enable production environments to leverage Gaia-X
USTUTT	InHPC-DE	A joint project of all three national HPC centres to set up a Gaia-X ecosystem close to high-performance computing infrastructures

FBU	EUCloudEdgeIoT	Building the European Cloud, Edge & IoT Continuum for business and research
TOP-IX	FLUIDOS	Flexible, scaLable, secUre, and decentrallseD Operating System
UNIBO, FBU	HiPEAC Network	Bridging industry and academia in computing systems since 2004
UNIBO	EPI SGA2	Building Europe's high performance computing capabilities
UNIBO	EUPEX	European Pilot for Exascale
UNIBO	REGALE	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
UNIBO	ISOLDE	High Performance, Safe, Secure, Open-Source Leveraged RISC-V Domain-Specific Ecosystems
UNIBO	TRISTAN KDT	Together for RISC-V Technology and ApplicationS
MARUN, BIGTRI	BRIGHTER	Breakthrough in micro-bolometer imaging (Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)
MARUN, BIGTRI	LoLiPoP IoT	Long Life Power Platforms for Internet of Things (Horizon Europe - KDT - RIA)

7.4 Horizon Results Booster

DECICE plans to apply and use the support from the services of the [Horizon Results Booster](#) (HRB). HRB offers services in the areas of communication, dissemination and exploitation to EC-funded projects. The service is split into three modules. Module A supports the creation of a results portfolio suitable for dissemination, as well as the identification of similar ongoing projects to form a project group with. Module B focuses on the design of a joint dissemination plan for the project group formed as part of Module A as well as the actual dissemination of the results. Lastly, Module C offers support in the improvement of existing exploitation strategies with the aim to increase their effectiveness.

8. Communication Activities

Communication activities are a crucial part of the project to increase awareness of its results and thereby maximise the impact.

There are three main channels for project communication activities:

- In-person communication, for example at workshops, presentations, or meetings with relevant stakeholders;
- Offline channels, for example leaflets or posters;
- Online channels, for example websites, social media channels, newsletter, etc.

These channels are being used to spread project outcomes, build networks, evaluate ideas and gather feedback.

The communication activities carried out as part of the project can be categorised into three general areas:

- **Promotion:** Raising awareness about DECICE and its objectives, progress, results, and developments.
- **Involvement:** Engaging all relevant stakeholders in project activities to ensure their involvement in its progress.
- **Networking:** Forming strong and sustainable relationships in order to improve the long-term take-up of the DECICE developments.

Over the course of the project, all partners will carry out communication activities with the aim to maximise the awareness and impact of DECICE.

9. Monitoring and Evaluation of the Dissemination Process

9.1 Individual Dissemination and Communication Responsibilities

The responsibilities of each consortium partner regarding dissemination and communication activities can be summed up as follows.

- Provision of at least 12 social media posts (one every three months per partner)
- Regularly creating news articles to generate traffic on website
- Continuous reporting of individual dissemination activities, including the following:
 - Posts on the organisations' websites
 - Posts on the organisations' social media channels
 - Newsletters
 - Attendance of events/presentations of DECICE
 - Publications
 - Video

If necessary to achieve the KPIs, SYNNO will request further content from the partners. The spreadsheets described in the following chapters are used to monitor the fulfilment of these responsibilities of the consortium partners.

9.2 Dissemination and Communication Management

To ensure that the news section of the project website as well as the social media channels are being updated regularly and the provision of content is being distributed between all partners, spreadsheets are being used to keep track of upcoming and past contributions. The spreadsheets have been set up by SYNNO, who is in charge of uploading all posts and articles, and have been made available to all partners. They are being used to allocate responsibilities for upcoming posts and articles as well as to keep an overview of all past activity. Figure 28 shows the spreadsheet that is being used to plan upcoming social media posts provided by all consortium partners and to keep track of past activities. It contains information about the posts such as the expected delivery date, the post date, the general context of the post, the channel on which it has been posted, and content-related information such as the post itself, hashtags, mentions, and included links, images and alt-text.

Figure 26: DECICE Spreadsheet Social Media Posts

The spreadsheet shown in Figure 29 is being used to keep track of the news articles posted on the DECICE project website. It contains information such as the expected delivery date for each article as well as the actual post date, title, author, proposed image and link of the article after publishing.

Figure 27: DECICE Spreadsheet News Articles

9.3 Planning, Steering, and Reporting

Event Spreadsheet

In order to plan and keep track of dissemination and communication activities as well as to meet the KPIs listed in section 8.4, several spreadsheets were set up in Google Sheets. These sheets are being used to plan and keep an overview of relevant events that might be of interest for consortium members, attended events, publications, and media activities. These spreadsheets are shared with all

partners and are being continuously updated as dissemination and communication activities are carried out. Each partner has the responsibility to enter their activities and related information into the relevant sheet.

The event spreadsheet shown in figure 30 is being continuously updated to keep track of upcoming events that might be of interest for the consortium, which partner is planning to join the event and present DECICE and where partners already attended and presented. This sheet will regularly be updated on the event subpage on the project website.

Figure 28: DECICE Spreadsheet Publications, Events, Media

Additionally, SYNYO created two worksheets for the publications that DECICE have to deliver for reaching the KPIs, press releases and peer reviewed publications. Those sheets provide an overview including the partner, delivery date, post date, title, author, reviewer, publisher, link etc.

Finally, the worksheet Media shows the sheet that is used to keep track of all media activities related to DECICE that are carried out by partners of the consortium. This includes, for example, newsletters, posts on the organisations’ websites, posts on the partners’ social media channels, publications that are no press releases or peer reviews publications (KPIs).

10. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) listed in table 9 have been established in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the project's dissemination activities according to the main goal of raising awareness about the project outcomes. The KPIs will be monitored regularly and allow the proper adjustment of the dissemination activities as the project progresses.

Table 8: Dissemination and Communication KPIs of DECICE

Activity	KPI	Success Indicator	Source and Methodology	Status
Project Website	Number of annual visits on the project website	10.000	News, Publications, Videos, Newsletters, Deliverables	In progress
Social Networks	Number of followers on social media	250	Keeping profiles on such networks active via regular posting and monitoring	In progress
Newsletter	Number of newsletter issues	9	Recording of subscribers to the electronic newsletter	In progress
Videos	Number of project YouTube videos	4	Introduction, informative and educational videos to support awareness creation and stakeholders' engagement	In progress
Workshops, Events, Webinars	Average number of participants per workshop*	30	Attendance proof, presented material, photos, animation of social media channels, events' reports depending on scope and co-location	In progress
Participation to Events and Presentations	Number of external events partners attended/promoted DECICE	10	Attendance proof, presented material, photos, animation of social media channels, events' reports	In progress
Press Releases / Publication in Press	Number of press releases Number of peer-reviewed publications	5 (in total)	A press/media kit will be developed containing detailed press releases, videos, publishable images, flyers Articles and papers presented and published in high-quality venues	In progress

*15 workshops/sessions/webinars including:

- 1 business models workshop (T6.1, M18-M24)
- 2 requirements workshops (T6.1, 1 in M3-M6, 2 in M7-M12),

- 6 co-organised webinars/workshops with other H2020 and/or HE funded projects (M1-M36)
- 1 final event for the presentation of the project results in collaboration with the other RIAs
- 3 training workshops (T6.1, M12-M36)
- 2 events to promote the project results (to reach the total of 15)
- 2 additional events – tba (to reach the total of 15)

11. Conclusion

D6.1 aims to summarize the channels, methods, means and activities to be carried out with the goal to maximize the project's impact through continuous dissemination and communication activities. The plan will be continuously reviewed and updated over the course of the project.

The deliverable provided an overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out and planned for the DECICE project. It identified relevant target groups and their tailored activities. Furthermore, an emphasis was put on the dissemination & communication plan of the project, including the aims and objectives as well as the process and the partners' individual dissemination plans. The report additionally provided an overview of the established visual design concept, including the colour scheme, logo, print materials and screen design. Furthermore, channels such as the DECICE project website, social media and newsletters are presented. Information was also provided on the project's dissemination activities. This included an overview of past and future events and planned publications. Moreover, an outline of the communication activities as well as an overview of the means of monitoring and evaluation have been given.

As the project is still at an early stage, this plan will be continuously reviewed, updated and adapted according to further developments.

Project Links

DECICE project website: <https://www.decice.eu/>

DECICE newsletter subscription: <https://bit.ly/decice-newsletter>

DECICE Twitter account: https://twitter.com/DECICE_EU

DECICE LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/decice-project-b0b55b25a/>

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